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Nature of Elections in Africa: A Review of Kenya and Zimbabwe Elections (2000-2020)

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Abstract

This research examines the persistent failure of electoral processes to ensure democratic consolidation in Africa, with specific focus on the Eastern African countries of Kenya and Zimbabwe over a 20 years period from 2000 to 2020. It contends that though periodic elections are a fundamental precept of representative democracy, their conduct in numerous African states is often marred by systematic deficiencies that undermine their integrity and legitimacy. The paper while employing a comparative historical analysis, discovers that flawed elections in these nations emanates from some deeply ingrained issues like the weaponization of ethnic identities (Kenya), state-sponsored violence and coercion (Zimbabwe), biased election management bodies,

partisan security agencies, and the pervasive manipulation of media and legal institutions to the interest of the incumbent. The research however unravels that elections, rather than serving as genuine expressions of public will, often function as rituals for the legitimization of entrenched power, leading to recurring post-election violence and political instability. The paper concludes that achieving democratic consolidation (in Africa) requires indeed substantive, not merely procedural, electoral integrity. It recommends comprehensive institutional reforms encompassing truly independent electoral management bodies (EMBs), the re-professionalization of security forces, effective judicial independence, equitable media access, and more robust, principled election observation team by regional bodies like the African Union and SADC to foster credible elections that reflect the reliable aspirations of the citizenry.

KEYWORDS: *Africa, Democracy, Election, Kenya, Violence, Zimbabwe*

Introduction

Periodic elections remain one of the basic tenets of representative democracy all over the world. Election occupies a pivotal point in the democratic space of any country as it provides avenue for legitimating of, and renewal of regimes on one hand and, on the other hand it offers the citizens the opportunities to remove any under-performing government and replace same with another. Eldman (1964) cited in Olorunsuwa, 2019:185) submits that while there is possibility of having elections without democracy, it is unthinkable impossible to have democracy without elections; hence elections are important and central to the functioning of modern democracy (Singh and Mishra 1991).

In Africa and largely in developing democracies, regularly held elections are indications of a liberal democratic journey, however, only regularly held elections infused with appreciable, cumulative and substantial integrity would lead to, and result in, the actualization of the objectives of democratic development which grants legitimacy to a government, that is an indispensable element for positive socio-political

developments in any given society (Jega,2019, Ogbeidi, 2010). Ideally, elections are meant to take place with highest consideration to some all-important factors like the existence of an unbiased election management body, providing a level playing ground for all aspirants and parties, neutral and professional security agencies, a well spelt out time table, a strong and enduring constitution and electoral laws as well as a fearless and robust judiciary to adjudicate electoral disputes and a free press to effectively inform the public. Additionally, elections are to hold within an atmosphere of serenity, tranquillity and peace. It is only in view of these enumerated conditions that citizens can freely exercise their powers of decision through elections, only under such conditions could the results of election can be said to reflect the wishes and aspiration of the people.

However, elections in Africa are largely chaotic, turbulent, violent, trouble laden (Hamer, 2013; Abati, 2022Wahman, 2023) and mostly disputed by losers who are always of the notion of being screwed at the poll. The quality of African elections continues to vary widely; however, some merely serve as an obligatory ritual by which leaders maintain their hold on power in their respective domains (Seigle, 2019). Elections and electioneering throughout the continent of Africa (perhaps with the exemption of Botswana, South Africa and Rwanda that have evolved a highly acceptable political culture of tolerance and a fairly developed electoral system that is largely trusted by politicians, the citizens and observers) have common denominator of massive malpractices and rigging that often result into deadly post- election violence. It is a common place for some leaders to ensure tardiness before elections are conducted in order to stay in power for as long as they could, while those that conduct elections within reasonable time limit put in place measures that makes it almost impossible for anyone else to defeat them in the elections (Ogbeidi, 2010). In 2019, elections were held in 20 African countries (Siegle, 2019) and the nature of how this election were conducted varies across borders but most of them returned almost the same verdict of un-standardised polls that drew the condemnation of foreign and domestic observers (Ogbeidi, 2010). Elections in African countries have always attracted international and

local concerns especially in Kenya and Zimbabwe where thousands of people have died and hundreds of others have been rendered homeless due to the attendant crises of flawed elections.

It is in view of these identified challenges and the need to avoid a repeat of the past that this paper seeks to: i. Interrogate the conditions that encourage failed electoral processes across the continent of Africa with a focus on Zimbabwe and Kenya, ii. What are the immediate and remote causes of failed elections in these Africa states; and iii. to suggest what can be done to cause tremendous improvement in the future African elections in order to encourage democratic consolidation.

Literature Review

Election

There seems to be a general notion among scholars about what election is, however, it has been variously conceptualized by authors, scholars, politicians and observers alike. Kapur (2009) defines election is a prepared periodic event in which an individual or group of individuals is(are) elected or voted for into a given office. The periodic election is an accepted norm and standard of global practice and method for regime legitimating to determines who gets power or control policy making. This explains why in Africa; elections are considered to be a do or die affair. Okoye (2003) noted that “*elections are a complex set of activities with different variables that act and feed on one another. It can be defined as a ‘formal’ act of collective decision that occurs in a stream of connected antecedent and subsequent behaviour*”.

To the duo of R. Dowse and J. Hughes (1972), election is a form of social mechanism, for the aggregation of preferences of a particular kind. Election can thus be seen as a periodically organized political event for the purpose of either legitimating an existing government for another term or for the enthronement of a new regime through voting.

Elections in Africa: History, Nature and Manifestations

Elections in Africa emerged as part of colonial legacy and as a mechanism for the institutional transfer of the superstructure of liberal democracy to African societies in the early part of the twentieth century. In Nigeria for instance in 1922, the Clifford constitution introduced elective principle to the Legislative Assembly (Jinadu, 1995: 76, cited in Adejumobi, 2000; Adejumobi 2000; Nwosu, Olaniyi and Oyedele,1998). This trend was similar in all colonial enclaves across Africa. It is therefore safe to conclude that election represents one of the colonial legacies bequeathed to the African continent by the colonialists.

Jega (2019) describes elections in Africa as being ‘deficit of electoral integrity’, as there is failure in the electoral process to entrench good governance, stable and sustainable democratic political systems; because, elections are deeply embedded in lots of unwholesome practices, such as the pervasive use of money, violence, power of incumbency, and a whole lots of electoral malpractices and fraudulent activities in the electoral process. All these according to Jega (2019) grossly undermines the usefulness of elections as a vehicle for liberal democratic development. He further asserts that the mere periodic ritual of regular conduct of elections does not, in itself, bring about desirable democratic development, unless the electoral process, as well as participation by stakeholders in the elections have integrity which yields substantive results and enduring benefits to the majority of the citizens. Jega concludes that elections in Africa in virtually all cases are ritualistic periodical exercises which are devoid of integrity and merely serve the function of legalizing or legitimizing the access and control of government power by people who are largely unconcerned with, or are indifferent to the requirements of sustainable democratic advancement and growth. Ogbeidi (2010), in his assessment of the nature of election in Africa concludes that our culture of electoral process is nothing but a ‘failed culture’ that have not being able to engender enduring democratic legacies throughout the continent of Africa; as elections are usually conducted under the atmosphere of violence and bitterness.

Noting further, Ogbeyidi(2010) that all elections so far conducted have been marred by serious problems of vote rigging, electoral violence, voters' intimidation, manipulation by electoral officers, and falsification of election results among others. He opined further that the greed of politician for control of state power which gives them unfettered access to the economy and the wealth of the country has made elections become a mere means of transferring political power for economic gains. This is the reason why elections assume a violent and bitter nature in Africa. Elections in Africa since its inception therefore has been characterized by violence and bitterness as epitomized by Kenya and Zimbabwe elections; Côte d'Ivoire election of 2010-2011 and 2011 general elections in Nigeria. The bitterness and violence that characterised these elections have led to the death thousands of citizens and the displacement of hundreds of thousands of people in those countries (IPI 2011).

Adejumobi (2010), while giving his thought on elections in Africa, he traced the foundational lapses of electoral woes that has befallen the African continent to the doorstep of the colonialists when he averred that undignified politics of de-participation and the shrinking of the electoral space which has become a notable feature of the African post-colonial era has its roots in earlier colonial history of the continent. He intrinsically reinforced his position in the following words. From the foregoing, Africa has developed a culture of failed elections that are marred with low political participation and a bitter attitude towards the government due to the violent nature of the electoral process.

Elections in Kenya in Historical Perspective

Looking into history, Kenya's journey to freedom was ruthless, violent and bloody as the Kenya African Union (KAU)'s Mau Mau movement which coordinated anti colonialist rebellion activities was constantly crushed by the colonialists. Several of the leaders of the movement were incarcerated with about 8,000 people reported detained, while a large number of people were reported killed (Richardson, 2023, Roger, 2022). Jomo Kenyata a leading anti-colonial struggle was imprisoned

for 7 years in 1952 after which KAU was proscribed. Another leading figure of KAU, Dedan Kimathi was arrested and hanged by the colonialists in 1956 for his role in the Mau Mau uprising. As a way of putting the incessant Mau rebellion under control by the British, Kenya was put under state of emergency from 1952 -1959(Jalloh, 2022). This however did not diminish the resolve of the Kenyans to continue to demand for self-government through guerrilla activities. Hence in 1954 all three races (European, Asian and African) were admitted into the Kenya Legislative Council (Talamantes, 2018; World History, 2020a; The Commonwealth).

The first elections in Kenya were held in 1957 to fill the Africans seats to the Legislative Council (Kiano, n.d.; Mboya, 1958; International Foundation for Electoral System (2008)). A transitional constitution was introduced in 1960, which allowed for political party's participation in the political space. The transition constitution gave Africans majority seats in the Legislative Council. Jomo Kenyatta was released in 1962 to become Kenya's first Prime Minister on December 12, 1963 at independence (Embassy of Kenya, 2020; World History, 2020a). In 1964 Kenya became a Republic with Kenyatta becoming its first President under a new constitution (World History, 2020a). An opposition leftist party, the Kenya People's Union (KPU) was formed in 1966 by Oginga Odinga a former Vice President and Luo elder (Embassy of Kenya, 2020; World History, 2020a). The opposition was shot lived as it was banned shortly thereafter and its leaders were arrested in 1969. Hence Kenya became a "de facto" single party state which was constitutionally backed in 1982 but repealed in 1991. Kenyatta's death in August 1978, brought Vice President Daniel arap Moi as Kenya's second President (Embassy of Kenya, 2020; World History, 2020a).

Failed Electoral Process and Election Crises in Kenya (2000-2020)

Daniel Arap Moi's reign as the 2nd Kenyan President between 1978-2002 laid a solid foundation for future political turmoil in Kenya.

Anderson and Lochery cited in Cheeseman (2008) buttressed this point when they held that:

“the large-scale instrumental use of political violence, structured along ethnic lines and fuelled by notions of *majimbo*, was introduced to Kenya by Daniel Arap Moi and then fostered by the willingness of political leaders of all persuasions to sponsor and tolerate the existence of militias”.

His 1988 2nd term election victory raised ethnic tensions in some rural areas due to perceived highhandedness. The government embarked on series of political reforms in 1986 that included the scrapping and replacement of secret ballot for open ballot in parliamentary elections, centralisation of the civil and judicial services under the presidency among others. His presidency demonstrated high intolerance for opposition. Foreign aids were suspended from 1991, as a result of the dissatisfaction among donors due to human rights abuses and worsened economic conditions.

The political space was however liberalized (as it was in most other African countries), amidst strong pressure for multiparty elections. Several new political parties emerged, competing in the December 1992 polls with KANU in the first multiparty elections in Kenya after independence. Notable of the new parties were Forum for the Restoration of Democracy (FORD–Kenya), led by Oginga Odinga, the Democratic Party led by Mwai Kibaki, and FORD–Asili led by Kenneth Matiba (World History, 2020a; The Commonwealth, 2020). The 1992 elections were largely flawed that a Commonwealth observer group at the elections concluded that “*they were flawed, but sufficiently free and fair for the results to be acceptable as the democratic will. KANU led by Daniel Arap Moi won, against a divided opposition*” (World History, 2020a).

The Kenya presidential and parliamentary elections of 2002 brought about a new dawn in the Kenyan political space as the KANU that has ruled the country for 39 years since her independence was humbled at the poll by a newly formed National Rainbow Coalition (NARC) under

the leadership of Kibaki and Raila Odinga garnering 63% of the votes to defeat Uhuru Kenyata who was nominated to succeed Moi in KANU scoring 20% of the votes(Anderson, 2003 and Marc, 2002).

Post- Election Turmoil of 2007-2008

In Kenya, the main defining feature of political activities, apart from colonial legacy of deprivations, violence and exclusion, is ethnicity and land (Cooke, 2009, the Carter Center, 2013). Flint re-echoed in Cheeseman (2008) agrees with this in his submission that “salient ethno-regional identities reinforced by historical grievances over land ownership, economic inequality, and political exclusion, are central to an understanding of the Kenya crisis...” Kenya with an ethnic colouration of Kikuyu tribe having about 22% of the population, Luhya 14%, Luo 13%, Kalenjin 12% and Kamba 11%(Lafargue, and Katumanga,2008, The Carter Center, 2013), there is consistent inter-ethnic wrangling among them about the control of government power which has come to be a defining trigger for the culture of political violence which climax mostly during elections, especially since the advent of multiparty politics in 1991(The Carter Center, 2013).

The alliance between Democratic Party's (DP) Mwai Kibaki and Raila Odinga's National Democratic Party (NDP) broke down due to irreconcilable differences surrounding betrayal of agreement between Odinga and Kibaki that in return for Odinga's support, Kibaki would support the passage of a constitution that would devolve power from the presidency and create a new and fully empowered position of Prime Minister, which Odinga would assume. An agreement that Kibaki reneged. This distrust between the two leaders and the ambition of the duo pulled them apart. Kibaki went back to Moi his former ally for political assistance for an alliance with Kenyan African National Union (KANU), FORD-Kenya, and a number of smaller parties including Safina and New FORD-Kenya under the banner of Party of National Unity (PNU) (Murunga, and. Nasong'o, 2006, Cheeseman, 2008). Odinga formed Orange Democratic Movement (ODM) which like the NARC represented a broad coalition movement with the likes of former allies of Kibaki, such as Charity Ngilu and Najib Balala, as well as

former Moi loyalists, such as Musalia Mudavadi (Cheeseman, 2008). The electioneering process leading to the 2007 election was tough and heated with a number of issues. While ethno-regional sentiment was fully deployed into political discussions and campaigns, the presidential race between President Kibaki from Kikuyu ethnic extraction and Odinga from the Luo ethnic group (Lafargue, and Katumanga, 2008), has reinforced the known culture of intra-ethnic rivalry between the cultural groups in Kenya. With instances of violence during campaigns claiming about 600 lives (ICP), there are a number of other factors such as faulty opinion polls and the introduction and the use of social media platforms for campaigns. These in no small measure propelled the heightened violence that followed the election. For instance, the final Steadman poll placed Odinga on 45 per cent of the vote, while Kibaki was behind him with 43 per cent. While some of the opinion polls had predicted a tight and keenly contested race between Kibaki and his former ally Odinga, some other ones have suggested Odinga as the winner of the poll. When the result of the poll was in the contrary, the supporters of ODM resulted into violence alleging a rigged poll (Cheeseman, 2008). The use of the social media and mobile phones in peddling rumour untamed and activities of jobless youth who had buried their hope in the presidency of Odinga increased the fatality of the poll and subsequent outbreak of violence (Lafargue, and Katumanga, 2008).

The events leading to the election has indicated that Kibaki's second term ambition was in serious danger as his new alliance was significantly weak compared to the NARC that brought him on board in a number of ways. The loss of Odinga, Musyoka, and Ngilu, left Kibaki had dealt a big blow to the wider ethno-regional support base he enjoyed during the 2002 elections. This is because at the presidential level Kenyan communities have historical political behavior of unwilling to vote for a party that does not have any of their tribal leaders within its ranks (Cheeseman, 2008). The poll abinitio look too good to be won by Kibaki as lots of factors have come to play against effective coordination of the president's campaign.

Going by the release of the first batch of declared results from ODM strongholds, Odinga was maintaining a comfortable lead. However, as results from constituencies favourable to Kibaki began to be announced by the Electoral Commission of Kenya (ECK), Kibaki was leading Odinga in a narrow win. The chairman of the ECK, Samuel Kivuitu, who later confessed of being pressured to announce the result, eventually went ahead to declare Kibaki the winner with 4,584,721 to Odinga's 4,352,993 in spite of protestations of the ODM and the EU that there were irregularities and discrepancies in the tallying and collation of the results. It was observed that in Molo and Kieni constituencies the figures given to EU observers were over 20,000 lower than the figures later released by the ECK, and election monitors were denied entrance in some collation units. The head of the EU observation team personally reported that he has seen result forms for the Lari and Kandara constituencies in which the final figure had been changed to favour Kibaki among other instances (Lafargue, and Katumanga, Cooke, 2009).

Considering the number of seats won by the two leading parties, it looks pretty difficult for Kibaki's PNU to have won the presidential election in a poll conducted simultaneously. Reports from ECK indicated that in all, there were 206,897 more ballots cast in the presidential than the parliamentary which is suggestive of rigging in the poll by both candidates (Cheeseman, 2008). Though observers' reports had shown differently that Odinga actually won the poll. Unfortunately, upon the declaration of Kibaki as the winner of the poll, pro-Odinga supporters in the coast region of Kericho and in Nairobi, Rift Valley (Eldoret), Nyanza (Kisumu), Coast Province (Mombasa), Naivasha and Nakuru went in flames of violence which eventually claimed about a thousand of lives and leaving hundreds displaced with an unknown number of women sexually abused similar to the 1992 and 1997 elections that witnessed such level of death and displacement (Lafargue and Katumanga; 2008, Cheeseman, 2008; Cooke, 2009; IPI, 2011; the Carter Centre, 2013). The carnage continued until 28 February, 2008, when an accord was signed for the creation of the post of Prime Minister for the leader of the majority party in parliament and allocation

of about 10 cabinet posts to ODM through the efforts of Koffi Anan African Union delegation (Cooke, 2009; The Carter Centre, 2013).

Table i . 2007 Presidential Election Result

Candidate (Party) [Coalition]	Number of Votes	% of Votes
Mwai Kibaki (DP) [PNU]	4,584,721	46.42%
Raila Odinga (ODM)	4,352,993	44.07%
Kalonzo Musyoka (ODM-K)	879,903	8.91%
Joseph Karani (KPTP)	21,171	0.21%
Pius Muiru (KPP)	9,667	0.10%
Nazlin Omar (WCP)	8,624	0.09%
Kenneth Matiba (SSA)	8,046	0.08%
David Waweru Ng'ethe (CCU)	5,976	0.06%
Nixon Kukubo (RPK)	5,927	0.06%

Table ii. 2007 National Assembly Election Result

Party/[Coalition]	Number of Seats (210)*
Orange Democratic Movement (ODM) & Allies	102
National Rainbow Coalition (NARC)	3
Party of National Unity (PNU)	43
Others	62

Source: <http://africanelections.tripod.com/ke.html>

2013 and 2018 Kenyan Elections

The protracted election violence of 2007-2008 and the subsequent externally mediated peace accord between the Kibaki and Odinga groups laid a solid foundation for some basic reforms that defined future political engagement of Kenyans. The reforms climaxed in the ratification of the constitution amendment in August 2010. The new constitution established a new electoral body known as Independent Electoral and Boundary Commission (IEBC), a 68-member senate was introduced and the representative membership was increased from 222 to 350.

The 2013 general elections were strictly a race between two presidential candidates, Raila Odinga of CORD coalition and Uhuru Kenyatta of Jubilee coalition. The IEBC's official results showed a narrow margin of victory for Kenyatta (Jubilee) with 50.07% of the vote, while Odinga (CORD) garnered 43.31% (Schulz-Herzenberg, Aling'o and Gatimu, 2015). The election was clear departure from the previous ones

(especially 2007 election) as electioneering process was largely peaceful and the election results were adjudged free and representing the democratic will of the Kenyans. The Independent Electoral and Boundaries Commission IEBC was seen to be largely impartial and fair in its activities (The Carter Center, 2013). The Jubilee Alliance of Kenyatta secured comfortable majority in both houses of the National Assembly which was indicative that the party actually won the presidential election unlike in 2007 when reverse was the case. Though cases of rigging and irregularities were lodged to the Supreme Court by Odinga but the court upheld the decision of the IEBC (Kumenyi, 2013; Schulz-Herzenberg, Aling'o and Gatimu, 2015).

The 2017 elections were marred by serious human rights abuses by Kenyan security agencies, which used brute force to disperse protests that was sparked by the announcement of the result. State sponsored terror was unleashed in opposition strongholds in Nairobi and Western Kenya in a house-to-house operations. Not fewer than 12 people were killed by police in Western Counties of Kisumu and Siaya and another 33 in Nairobi during the violence, in all over 60 people were murdered in political violence in three months (HRW, 2017 and Jason, 2017). The campaigns have indicated some level occurrences of violence. The vice president's country home, Mr. Williams Ruto was attacked, and there was a reported case of a politically motivated murder of Mr. Chris Msando, the head of information, communication and technology at the Independent Electoral and Boundaries Commission (IEBC) 2 days before the polls. There were reports of plans to rig the vote in favour of the incumbent President, and series of staged armed raid on one of the opposition's rallying center (Jason, 2017b, Baker, 2017) among other anomalies had characterized election.

The opposition coalition, National Super Alliance (NASA)'s presidential candidate Odinga, had rejected Uhuru Kenyatta's victory and proceeded to the Supreme Court for redress citing instance of non-compliance with the electoral laws. On September 1 Supreme Court nullified the August 8 elections and ordered a fresh poll within 60 days. The commission had declared President Uhuru Kenyatta the winner

with over 54 percent of votes. The IEBC scheduled fresh elections for October 26, but Odinga announced his withdrawal from the race on October 10 citing the refusal of IEBC to reform the commission (HRW, 2017). In a twist of event Odinga offered himself in February to be sworn-in by some lawyers as the 'Kenyan people's president' after the apex court threw out his case against Kenyatta victory in the October 26th re-run poll that he boycotted. This signaled the beginning of another round of election induced violence that has come to be one of the features of Kenya electoral landscape from the 90s (Jason, 2018). Uhuru and Raila later met in a peace meeting in March 2018 where a joint statement was issued on the possible peaceful resolution of the issue (The Guardian March 9, 2018).

Elections in Zimbabwe (2000-2020)

Zimbabwe's first multi-party election was held in the eve of her independence in 1980, an election that Robert Mugabe led Zimbabwe African National Union (ZANU) won with 57 seats in the 80 members House of Assembly (against the desire of the colonialists) to defeat the Zimbabwe African People's Union (ZAPU) of Joshua Nkomo that won 20 seats. Mugabe became the Prime Minister and Canaan Banana as the President (Kriger, 2005; Tendi, n.d.; World History, 2020b). Retrospectively, the Unilateral Declaration of Independence (UDI) issued in 1965 by white settlers from South Africa under the leadership of Mr. Ian Smith had generated guerilla activities targeted at the white minorities. This resulted into the imprisonment of Robert Mugabe and Joshua Nkomo till 1974. After the initial political hostilities between Nkomo and Mugabe, fuelled by tribal hostilities become a noticeable feature of Zimbabwe's political life, which later resulted into Mugabe dismissing Nkomo from his cabinet in 1982, in 1987 the two leaders resolved their differences by merging their parties as ZANU-PF. The merger paved way for Zimbabwe effectively becoming a one-party state. The constitution was amended to transmute Mugabe into an executive president with Nkomo as his vice president until his death in 1999 (World History, 2020b)

Previous elections have consolidated Mugabe's political grip of Zimbabwe until the formation of the Movement for Democratic Change (MDC) in 1999 by conglomerate of opposition forces. The new party was led by Morgan Tsvangirai a former leader of Zimbabwe Trade Union Congress (Alexander, 2000,). The new party in February 2000 ensured that Mugabe was defeated in a constitution amendment referendum by 54.7% against 45.3% margin. The government's reaction was state sponsored violence against the opposition forces. Tensions were flared up in dramatic fashion during the first part of 2000(Alexander, 2000; Kriger, 2007, World History, 2020b).

The ZANU (PF) ruling party employed the use of organized violence and intimidation of the opposition as its strategy of holding onto power since the general election of 1985(Lewanika, 2019. The gory, pitiful and pathetic incidence that led to the burning of the almost all the party offices of ZAPU, killing of ZAPU supporters and burning of houses belonging to opposition members in 1985 elections was captured by Kriger (2005). Multiple sources have reported that ZANU(PF), when faced with dwindling popularity among the citizens and international community; state sponsored violence has been a recurrent strategy of the party before, during and often after elections to punish constituencies that sympathized with the opposition (Kriger, 2005; Lewanika, 2019; World History, 2020a). In the 1990 elections Mr. Edgar Tekere, former Mugabe's Minister contested against Mugabe as the candidate of the Zimbabwe Unity Movement (ZUM). Tekere received unprecedented support for his opposition to Mugabe which led to massive election rigging by ZANU-PF in order for Mugabe to win. ZUM supporters were targets of violent attacks which resulted in the murder of five candidates. Some criminals convicted for attempted murder of Mr. Patrick Kombayi, the former Gweru Mayor who survived being shot in the lower abdomen were pardoned immediately afterwards (Matonhodze, 2013). This was a confirmation that that the killings had the backing of ZANU led government. 1996 presidential election was an easy ride for Mugabe as he won over 90% of the votes against Mr. Abel Muzorerwa of United Parties (UP) and ZANU-Ndonga leader Ndabaningi Sithole. Mugabe's overwhelming win was

as a result of Sithole and Muzorewa withdrawing their candidacies shortly before the election (though their names remained on the ballot). Sithole was under house arrest due to a cooked up against him of assassination attempt on the Mugabe (Matonhodze, 2013)

The situation got to an alarming magnitude in the June 2000 elections as they were held amid widespread intimidation and humiliation of voters and violence by the Government and ZANU-PF supporters (Kriger, 2005, global security.org). The period before the 2000 parliamentary elections, going by the painful defeat of the government in the February referendum, have witnessed unprecedented violence by security forces backed (by Government)(Zimbabwe Human Rights NGO Forum, 2001; Amani Trust, n.d; U.S. Department of State, 2017), which implemented a planned and systematic campaign of intimidation and physical violence in the opposition strongholds which were manifested in ruling party supporters and war veterans occupation of commercial farms, and in some cases they killed, abducted, tortured, beat, abused, raped, and threatened farm owners, their workers, opposition party members, and other persons believed to be sympathetic to the opposition(ZHRFN, 2001, Alexander, 2000 and Amani Trust, nd).

There were reports of politically motivated disappearances; about 31 people (mostly members and sympathizers of MDC were killed between February and June and the police failed to make any arrest (Alexander, 2000). The Government invoked series of order to bar cross-constituencies movement of political supporters and restrict public gatherings. There were reports that non-Zimbabwean farm workers were threatened with deportation if they failed to vote the ruling party. The Movement for Democratic Change (MDC) in spite of the vote-rigging and other irregularities captured 57 out of the 120 seats (Alexander, 2000, www.global security.org). The MDC filed petitions in the High Court challenging the electoral results in 36 parliamentary constituencies alleging intimidation, vote-rigging, and other irregularities in those constituencies. The result of 6 of those constituencies were however overturned in favour of MDC (global

security.org). Mugabe later won the February 2002 presidential election with 56.2% of the vote amidst crises and irregularities. Though the poll was adjudged as “transparent, credible, free and fair” by AU, but the conduct of the election was strongly criticized by the Commonwealth, and other western government, Zimbabwean opposition personalities and other western media (Matonhodze, 2013).

The 2008 elections came with a lot of drama as the result of the election was withheld for more than 4 weeks (Southal, 2013). MDC who was confident it had won the poll unsuccessfully approached the court to compel the release of the result. The three major candidates – the incumbent Mugabe (Zanu PF), Tsvangirai (MDC), and Simba Makoni, an independent candidate failed to secure an outright majority in the poll in the first round of the poll. A second round was held on 27 June 2008 between Tsvangirai (with 48% of the first-round vote) and Mugabe (43%). The MDC candidate, Tsvangirai withdrew from the second round some days before the re-scheduled date, citing violence against his party’s supporters as the reason. The second round was won by Mugabe without Tsvangirai’s participation amidst of widespread condemnation. The period between the first and second round was marked by political violence for which ZANU-PF and the MDC traded blames. The Western governments and prominent Western organizations however put the blames on ZANU -PF for the violence (Matonhodze, 2013, Southal, 2013).

Considering the political exigencies of the time, Mugabe had no choice but to accept the political solution of a unity government offered by regional and international communities especially considering a widely condemned election victory, with a parliament without two-thirds majority of his ZANU- PF, and a recognized first round result in which Tsvangirai was leading. A unity government took office on February 2009 with Tsvangirai as the Prime Minister (Matonhodze, 2013).

Seeming to a swift twist of fate, the 31 July, 2013 elections saw Mugabe defeating Tsvangirai by a large margin of 61.1 per cent to 33 percent in the first-round presidential poll. This was matched with the

National Assembly and Senate results. The 'brilliant' performance in the presidential poll was replicated in the other two elections held simultaneously with the presidential poll. ZANU-PF secured a landslide victory, winning a total of 197 seats compared to 70 for the MDC-T, 2 seat was won by the MDC-M (a faction of MDC lead by Prof Ncube and a seat went to an independent candidate in the 270 members National Assembly. In the Senate elections, ZANU-PF won 37 seats while the MDC that won 21 seats (Southal, 2013, Polgreen, 2013).

Morgan Tsvangirai, the outgoing Prime Minister in the power sharing arrangement, described the result as "null and void" maintaining that his crushing election defeat was an orchestrated rigging by the Zimbabwe Electoral Commission (ZEC) and the registrar general's office, that managed the voters registration exercise(The Guardian, 2013). As captured Mandaza (2013), unlike the previous elections that were characterised by excessive killing and maiming of MDC supporters, and harassment of voters, the 2013 election was largely peaceful, except for police continued suppression of free expression, association and assembly throughout the year, arbitrary arrest, unlawful detentions and politically motivated prosecutions however continued. Although incidences of mass political violence greatly declined in the electioneering process, not fewer than 300 people were injured as a result of politically motivated acts of torture and other brutality (Amnesty International, 2013). However, ZANU appeared to have perfected another rigging method by grossly inflating the voters register especially in Mugabe's strongholds. To support this assertion the MDC later complained that it discovered series of anomalies on the voters roll which include: 838,000 entries having the same names, addresses and dates of birth but with different ID numbers; 350,000 people who are more than 85 years old and another 109,000 people aged over 100 - including a 135-year-old army office. The security services that voted two weeks earlier returned a result of 60,000 votes against the official figure of 33,000 on the pay role for the police force (BBC, 2013) see figure 1.

Figure 1

Last Name	First Name	Sex	D.O.B	Age
S	WINNIE	F		45.3
S	WINNIE	F		45.3
M	LINDIWE	F		57.3
M	LINDIWE	F		57.3
S	SIBONGILE	F		39.3
S	SIBONGILE	F		39.3
A	FABBY	F		69.1
A	FABBY	F		69.1
M	LINDIWE	F		39.1
M	LINDIWE	F		39.1
M	LETINA	F		28.1
M	LETINA	F		28.1
M	LINDIWE	F		40.2
M	LINDIWE	F		40.2
A	WILBERT	M		39.2
A	WILBERT	M		39.2
S	JOHN	M		71.5
S	JOHN	M		71.5

Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-23591941>

The voter’s roll was not released to the parties until the day before the vote, an act raising fears of fraud and considered as a deliberate attempt to conceal the duplicated names of the register (Polgreen, 2013)). The detected extraneous names on the voter’s roll are in huge excess of the 938,085 votes that gave Mugabe the win.

The media was effectively screwed in favour of the ruling SANU-PF as the state-run television (ZBC) was providing live coverage to President Mugabe's rallies while Mr. Tsvangirai's campaign was never aired. The MDC media support was in the privately owned newspapers; however, the majority of Zimbabweans are too poor afford to buy newspapers (BBC,2013). The licensed non-state broadcasters are close allies and sympathizers of ZANU-PF as such never also provided MDC and its candidate media coverage for the election, invariably, many Zimbabweans especially in the rural areas only saw and heard negative

coverage of Mr. Tsvangirai and praise for Mr. Mugabe during the campaign (BBC, 2013). The AU observers report indicated a worrisome nationwide high number of ‘assisted voters’ in many polling units. This was done on the alleged ground of illiteracy by the assisted voters, in a country that the United Nation rates as the most literate country in Africa. The AU mission gave the example of Muzarabani district in Mashonaland Central, where it observed 97 voters being assisted out of 370 assisted at one station, 77 out of 374 at a second station and 85 out of 374 at a third station. The MDC alleged that in Muzarabani North, out the 17,400 voters more than half of them were assisted. Lots of young voters- the group from which MDC drew its support base were excluded from the voters list and the number of ballot papers printed was 2.3 million in excess of the registered voters of 6.4 million which according to African Union is significantly higher than international best practices" which are between 5% and 10%(BBC, 2013). All these provide concerns for the sincerity of Zimbabwe Electoral Commission, which eventually cast doubt on the result of the election.

The election came with varied international opinion, with Western countries generally having reservation and condemnation for the poll. The mood of the Western nations was captured by Mr. John Kerry the American Secretary of State that *“in light of substantial electoral irregularities reported by domestic and regional observers, the United States does not believe that the results announced today represent a credible expression of the will of the Zimbabwean people”* (Polgreen, 2013). Meanwhile most African leaders with the exception of except Botswana congratulated Mr. Mugabe on his victory. Perhaps, the seeming agreement among African leaders about the said election being free, fair and largely represented the democratic wish of the people (which was reflected in the congratulatory messages to Mugabe) (Mandaza,2013). Explaining further, Mandaza captured the situation thus:

“Africans have reproduced their own versions of "observer missions" with the African Union, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) and the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa is hardly an improvement to celebrate. It constitutes a mere institutionalisation of failure, a glaring illustration that, throughout the continent, there is hardly any state or leader with the moral authority to judge or assess another's election.” (Mandaza,2013).

Mr. Robert Mugabe who has been earlier removed as the leader of his ZANU-PF party and placed under a week ‘house arrest’ by the military (which seem more like a coup) on the 14th of November 2017, finally put an end to his own 37 years rule on the 22nd November, 2017 through a letter of resignation sent to Jacob Mudenda, the Speaker of the House of Assembly moment after the ZANU-PF dominated House(with concurrence from the MDC opposition) party began impeachment to oust him from office. He was pressured to resign by his ZANU-PF or face impeachment. He was replaced by his former deputy, Emmerson Mnangagwa on 24th of November, 2017(Onishi, and Moyo, 2017; Dwyer and Kennedy, 2017; HRW, 2017, Latek, 2018)

The change of baton on the country leadership did not affect the timetable of the 2018 general elections. Mr. Mnangagwa was presented by ZANU-PF as its presidential candidate while, MDC featured Mr. Nelson Chamisa. The July 30th presidential and parliamentary elections, the first to be superintended by Mr. Mnangagwa were not any different from the previous ones. the European Union election monitors offered a significant and somber assessment of it as an "un-level playing field, intimidation of voters and lack of trust in the process undermined the pre-election environment" as what transpired in Zimbabwe before the election; this was witnessed in the ZANU-PF implemented strong intimidation tactics with reliance on the army who deployed 5,000 soldiers to rural areas months before the polls and the inversion of ZEC office by soldiers during tallying of votes(Mhaka,

2018, HRW, 2018, Latek, 2018). This effectively sends shivers into the spine of the support base of MDC. The opposition party had repeatedly complained about the flawed voters roll, ballot paper malpractices, voter intimidation, and bias by the electoral commission among other anomalies. Just moment before elections eighteen opposition officials were detained by police during a raid on the MDC's headquarters in Harare on (Jason, 2018b)

The Zimbabwe Electoral Commission (ZEC) declared ZANU PF victorious in both presidential and parliamentary elections. Mr. Mnangagwa scored 2.46m votes, (50.8%)of the 4.8m votes cast to defeat Nelson Chamisa, the candidate of the opposition Movement for Democratic Change party (MDC) who won 2.14m votes (44.3%); ZANU-PF got 144 seats, the MDC Alliance, won 64 seats, and one seat went to the National Patriotic Front, a new party formed by Mugabe loyalists after he was ousted (Jason, 2018(b), BBCb). The result of the elections was later affirmed by the court that has being highly politicized through the 2017 constitution amendment vesting the powers on the president to unilaterally appoint key members of the country members of the bench(Latek, 2018, HRW, 2018) As it is the electoral culture of Zimbabwe, opposition element thronged the street of Harare to protest the result of the parliamentary elections, in reaction, the Zimbabwe Defense Force used life ammunitions on the protesters killing 6 people in the process (Mhaka, 2018; BBC(b); HRW, 2018). The Media acted in the same manner they did in 2013 when ZANU was only accorded publicity (HRW, 2018; Latek, 2018).

Discussion of Findings and Conclusion

Events in the two countries under review have affirmed the view of Mandaza (2003) about Africa that post-colonial Africa is largely without the needed capabilities to put in place western modeled democracy upon which our credentials are measured. There is a long road yet to be travelled on the African democratic journey considering numerous ills that are against African seamless journey to effective democratic development. Kenya that has never witnessed military rule

unlike most African countries still suffers under the burden of political violence induced by flawed elections –a feature of a state’s undergoing early stage of democratic consolidation. The study has revealed a large-scale level of endemic electoral malpractices that is deeply engendered in the two countries under review. It has therefore come to the fore that the undemocratic conduct of elections stems from: firstly, the excessive poor performance of the political leaders which invariably awaken the spirit of distrust and discontent among the citizens; Secondly, the poor performances of the leaders and the seeming unavoidable electoral protest of citizens has awakened the spirit of fear in the leaders which invariably propels them to put in place all known mechanism for winning elections. The two countries have had distinct forms and characters that define their electoral and political histories.

In Kenyan, the multi-party democracy since 1991 has been defined by obvious three main trajectories: i. a voting habit and political culture that is patterned along ethnic lines; ii. a multi-party-political landscape that is rested on either pre- or post-election coalition political arrangements and iii. a very fragile polity centred around electoral dispute cum political violence that is influenced mostly by electoral malpractices and voting along ethnic affiliations.

Political events in Zambabwe since introduction of multi- party politics at independence in 1980 has being molded majorly by the shrewd character of Mugabe and his non-willingness to surrender power as evident in one of his speeches where he prided that only God can remove him from office (Onishi,N and Moyo, 2017). Despite dwindling popularity of Mugabe, he kept on winning elections through machiavelic acts of ruthlessness and violence. This he does through: i. the effective dispensing of crumbs to his cronies in ZANU-PF who saw him as the all-in-all and in return, accord him salvage loyalty. ii. Similar to this is the willingness of the leadership of the security formation to make themselves willing tools in the hand of Mugabe and ZANU-PF. The military has always assisted him to win elections by cruel humiliation and intimidation of the opposition. iii. He has consistently used economic matrix to appeal to the conscience of the locals by his

land redistribution policy. Due to this the rural areas remained the strongholds of ZANU-PF. iv. It is also expedient to note that the long years of relationship between Zimbabwe under Mugabe and China has yielded a lot of anti-democratic credentials for Zimbabwe. In the face of being ostracized by the western community, Mugabe has always found a dependable ally in China and she is Zimbabwe's fourth largest trading partner and her largest source of investment (Latek, 2018, Vines, 2018). Upon the imposition of sanction on Zimbabwe by EU in 2002, Mugabe had openly declared during a rally at the Chinese-built national stadium in Harare that: "We have turned east, where the sun rises, and given our back to the west, where the sun sets." Since this era, Chinese military investments in Zimbabwe have been enormous (Vine, 2018).

Recommendations

- i. There must be an urgent reorganization of the political structures through appropriate legislations and constitutional re-engineering to provide a level playing ground for all parties especially in term of access to media, security and fund.
- ii. Urgent re-orientation and reorganization of the security formations must be carried to purge the system of politically inclined officers so as to return the military fully back to the task of protection of the territorial integrity and maintenance of law and order in the countries.
- iii. There is also the urgent need for political re-orientation of Kenyans to consider capability as well as democratic credentials of candidates in elections and disregard ethnic considerations in making electoral decisions.
- iv. The regional bodies need to up their games in term of election monitoring. They should be sincere enough to openly condemned sham polls.
- v. The election management bodies (EMBs) in the two countries must gravitate towards professionalism such that they must not only be fair to all parties but must be seen to operating in fairness in dealing with all concerned.

- vi. The capacity of the judiciary to serve as an independent arbiter must be increased. This will ensure the continued trust of the citizens to have faith in it as the hope of the common man.

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